

COUPLED ANALYSIS OF THIN-WALLED COMPOSITE BEAMS BASED ON MULTISCALE ASYMPTOTIC FOUNDATION

J.-S. Kim^{1,*}, H. Kim²

¹ Dept. of Int. Mech. Eng., Kumoh Nat'l Inst. of Tech., Gumi, Korea,

² Dept. of Mech., Robotics and Energy Eng., Dongguk Univ.-Seoul, Seoul, Korea

* Corresponding author(junsik.kim@kumoh.ac.kr)

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1 Introduction

A slender beam structure has been found in various engineering fields, such as the spar of wing or blade in aerospace engineering and frame structure in mechanical and architectural engineering. In many cases, a classical beam theory (often called Euler-Bernoulli beam theory), in which the beam deformation is defined by the four strain measure associated with extension, bending and torsion, is sufficient to provide the design guideline. There are two situations where the classical theory is not adequate to apply; one is when the beam is weak in shear, the other is when the beam has a thin-walled open cross-section. The former can be resolved by applying Rankine-Timoshenko-type beam theories in which the transverse shear deformation is included, whereas the latter requires Vlasov-type beam theories that include the torsional warping restrained effect.

There have been many efforts associated with Rankine-Timoshenko-like theories [1, 2], whereas Vlasov-type theories have been paid less attention. Especially mathematically rigorous Vlasov-type models are very rare in literature, since they are not mathematically and/or asymptotically consistent with asymptotic displacement expansions. A way known so far to mathematically construct the Vlasov-like model is to promote the order of magnitude of the torsional warping related to the cross-sectional distortion [3]. Even though some efforts have been made to mathematically construct the Vlasov-like beam theories, there is a need to construct rigorously the beam model that can include accurately and efficiently the composite coupling effect when the beam is weak in shear and vulnerable to the cross-sectional distortion.

The objective of this paper is to present the procedure how to construct the Vlasov-like model via the asymptotic expansion method and the mixed

variational theorem. In this way, one can obtain the beam model that can consider both the shear deformation and the torsional warping restrained effect. The beam model obtained takes the form of a conventional Rankine-Timoshenko-Vlasov-like model, so that one can easily resolve the boundary condition issue [4] as well. The model is built upon the asymptotically expanded stress field and the intuitive engineering displacement field via the mixed variational theorem. This allows us to keep the asymptotically correctness as much as possible and the engineering simplicity. The asymptotic stress field is obtained by the computational asymptotic method [5,6]. Thus general anisotropic beams with arbitrary cross-sectional geometry can be easily handled.

2 Formulation

A generic uniform anisotropic beam, which is depicted in Fig. 1, is considered in this work. Unless it is not differently specified, Greek indices will take value in the set 2, 3, whereas Latin indices will take values in 1, 2, 3. The reference one-dimensional line is represented by x_1 , which is not necessarily to be on the elastic axis or the shear center, and the cross-sectional plane is denoted by x_α .

Fig. 1. A three-dimensional anisotropic beam

2.1 Mixed Variational Theorem

The Hellinger-Reissner functional is employed to systematically synthesize the asymptotic stress field and the intuitive engineering displacement field. The functional without a body force is then expressed by

$$\int_{S_\sigma} \int_{S_c} (\sigma_{ij} \delta \gamma_{ij} - (\varepsilon_{ij}^* - \varepsilon_{ij}) \delta \sigma_{ij}) dS dx_1 - \int_{S_\sigma} \bar{T}_i \delta u_i dS - \int_{S_u} (u_i - \bar{u}_i) \delta T_i dS = 0 \quad (1)$$

where ε_{ij} represents the strain tensor based on the displacements, whereas ε_{ij}^* does the one based on the stress tensor. The variables with the over bar are prescribed quantities. S_σ and S_u indicate the boundaries with prescribed tractions and prescribed displacements, respectively.

In what follows, how to construct both the stress field and the displacement field will be described.

2.2 Asymptotic Stress Field

According to the previous work [4-6], the asymptotic stress field can be obtained by taking the small parameter (ε) that is defined by the ratio of the beam characteristic length to the maximum cross-sectional dimension. The displacement is then expanded by

$$\mathbf{u}(x_i) = \mathbf{u}^{(0)}(y_1) + \varepsilon \mathbf{u}^{(1)}(y_i) + \varepsilon^2 \mathbf{u}^{(2)}(y_i) + \dots \quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}^{(0)}(y_1) &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & v_2^{(0)} & v_3^{(0)} \end{bmatrix}^t, \\ \mathbf{u}^{(k)}(y_i) &= \begin{bmatrix} u_1^{(k)} & u_2^{(k)} & u_3^{(k)} \end{bmatrix}^t, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

in which the displacement component $u_i^{(k)}$ is a function of y_i and $v_i^{(n)}$.

Subsequently the stress and strain expansions are obtained by employing Eq. (2) [5]. The final form of the stress field is expressed in terms of the classical strain measure (\mathbf{e}) which consists of the four components (an extensional strain, two bending curvatures and a torsional strain). That is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(0)} + \varepsilon \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(1)} + \varepsilon^2 \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(2)} + \varepsilon^3 \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(3)} + \dots \quad (4)$$

where the stress vectors at each order are calculated by [5]

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(k)}(y_i) = \sum_{n=1}^k \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(n)}(y_\alpha) \partial_{y_1}^{n-1} \mathbf{e}^{(k-n-1)}(y_1) \quad (5)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau}^{(k)}$ contains the cross-sectional warping function [5,6]. The strain measure at each order is given by

$$\mathbf{e}^{(k)} = \begin{bmatrix} v_{1,1}^{(k)} & v_{2,11}^{(k-1)} & v_{3,11}^{(k-1)} & \phi_{,1}^{(k)} \end{bmatrix}^t \quad (6)$$

Substituting Eq. (5) into Eq. (4), neglecting the higher-order classical strain measure, setting the small parameter the unity, and rearranging the equation yield

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(1)} \mathbf{e} + \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(2)} \mathbf{e}_{,1} + \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(3)} \mathbf{e}_{,11} + \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(4)} \mathbf{e}_{,111} + \dots \quad (7)$$

where the global classical strain measure can be now expressed by dropping the superscripts as follows:

$$\mathbf{e} = \begin{bmatrix} v_{1,1} & v_{2,11} & v_{3,11} & \phi_{,1} \end{bmatrix}^t \quad (8)$$

Notice in Eq. (7) that the higher-order strain measure is neglected, because its effect is relatively small for the thin-walled beam. Equation (7) will be regarded as the independent stress field in the mixed variational theorem. The classical strain measure (\mathbf{e}) is the unknown variable, which will be connected to the intuitive displacement field. The detailed derivation of Eqs. (5) and (7) can be found in the references [5,6].

2.3 Intuitive Displacement Field

The displacement field is intuitively assumed to have the form of a classical Rankine-Timoshenko model superimposing the torsional warping function, which is obtained by the computational asymptotic method [5], in order to consider the warping restraint effect (or Vlasov torsion).

The displacement field is then expressed by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_1(x_i) \\ u_2(x_i) \\ u_3(x_i) \end{Bmatrix} = \boldsymbol{\Theta}(y_\alpha) \tilde{\mathbf{v}}(y_1) + \mathbf{W}(y_\alpha) \phi_{,1} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\Theta(y_\alpha) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & y_2 & y_3 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -y_3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & y_2 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{W}(y_\alpha) = [w_1^\phi \quad w_2^\phi \quad w_3^\phi]^t,$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{v}} = [\tilde{v}_1 \quad \tilde{v}_2 \quad \tilde{v}_3 \quad \tilde{\phi} \quad \theta_1 \quad \theta_2]^t$$

in which the torsional warping function $\mathbf{W}(y_\alpha)$ is obtained from the asymptotic expansion method [5,6]. In this way, the restrained warping or Vlasov torsion can be properly incorporated into the intuitive displacement field.

The strains based on Eq. (9) are calculated by

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = \mathcal{L}_{TV} \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{TV} = (\mathcal{L}_T + \mathcal{L}_{23} \tilde{\Gamma}_\phi + \mathcal{L}_1 \tilde{\Gamma}_{\phi'}) \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{TV} \quad (11)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\gamma}^{RTV} = [\tilde{v}_{1,1} \quad \tilde{v}_{2,1} + \theta_2 \quad \tilde{v}_{3,1} + \theta_3 \quad \tilde{\phi}_{,1} \quad \theta_{2,1} \quad \theta_{3,1} \quad \tilde{\phi}_{,11}]^t \quad (12)$$

and the other matrices are defined in Appendix.

In Eq. (9), the torsional warping function w_i is expressed in terms of the first derivative of ϕ with respect to the axial coordinate. Thus the number of primary variables in Eqs. (9) and (12) is only six, which is the same as a generalized beam theory. In the finite element implementation, the total number of degrees of freedom will be seven due to the C^1 continuity of the torsional degree of freedom.

2.4 Rankine-Timoshenko-Vlasov model

Once the independent stress field and the displacement field are obtained, one can now derive the Rankine-Timoshenko-Vlasov model.

Substituting Eqs. (7), (9) and (11) into Eq. (1) yields

$$\int_{x_1} \int_{S_c} (\delta \boldsymbol{\gamma}' \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}' (\boldsymbol{\gamma}^* - \boldsymbol{\gamma})) dS \, dx_1 - \int_{S_\sigma} \delta \mathbf{u}' \bar{\mathbf{T}} dS - \int_{S_u} \delta \mathbf{T}' (\mathbf{u} - \bar{\mathbf{u}}) dS = 0 \quad (13)$$

where the highlighted equation is associated with the boundary condition, which indicates the traction weighted average boundary condition instead of the three-dimensional one. The remaining equations without the loading term are expanded as follows:

$$\langle \delta \boldsymbol{\gamma}' \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle = \delta \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{TV}^T \left[\langle \mathcal{L}_{TV}^\alpha \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(1)} \rangle \mathbf{e} + \langle \mathcal{L}_{TV}^\alpha \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(2)} \rangle \mathbf{e}_{,1} + \langle \mathcal{L}_{TV}^\alpha \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(3)} \rangle \mathbf{e}_{,11} + \dots \right] \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}' (\boldsymbol{\gamma}^* - \boldsymbol{\gamma}) \rangle \\ &= \delta \mathbf{e}' \left(\langle \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(1)'} \mathbf{S} \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(1)} \rangle \mathbf{e} + \langle \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(1)'} \mathbf{S} \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(2)} \rangle \mathbf{e}_{,1} + \dots - \langle \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(1)'} \mathbf{S} \mathcal{L}_{TV} \rangle \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{TV} \right) \\ &+ \delta \mathbf{e}'_{,1} \left(\langle \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(2)'} \mathbf{S} \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(1)} \rangle \mathbf{e} + \langle \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(2)'} \mathbf{S} \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(2)} \rangle \mathbf{e}_{,1} + \dots - \langle \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(1)'} \mathbf{S} \mathcal{L}_{TV} \rangle \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{TV} \right) \\ &+ \dots \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Equation (15) provides the relationship between the intuitive displacement field and the asymptotic stress field. One can see that these constraint equations take the form of $\mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{B}$, and the matrix of \mathbf{A} is a square matrix and is not a singular one. Thus \mathbf{x} vector whose components are the strain measure and its derivatives can be found by solving the simultaneous equation. Then the strain measure and its derivatives in the asymptotic strain field are expressed by the strain vector associated with the intuitive displacement field. The relationship obtained can be written in the form of

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{T}^{(0)} \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{TV}, \quad \mathbf{e}_{,1} = \mathbf{T}^{(1)} \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{TV}, \quad \mathbf{e}_{,11} = \mathbf{T}^{(2)} \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{TV}, \dots \quad (16)$$

Substituting Eq. (16) into Eq. (14) yields

$$\langle \delta \boldsymbol{\gamma}' \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle = \delta \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{TV}^T \mathbf{K}_{TV} \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{TV} \quad (17)$$

where

$$\mathbf{K}_{TV} = \langle \mathcal{L}_{TV}^\alpha \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(1)} \rangle \mathbf{T}^{(0)} + \langle \mathcal{L}_{TV}^\alpha \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(2)} \rangle \mathbf{T}^{(1)} + \langle \mathcal{L}_{TV}^\alpha \boldsymbol{\tau}^{(3)} \rangle \mathbf{T}^{(2)} \dots \quad (18)$$

As seen in Eq. (18), one can add the asymptotic stress up to any desired order to the stiffness matrix of the Rankine-Timoshenko-Vlasov model. However there is a numerical issue such that the rank of the matrix \mathbf{A} becomes less when the higher order stress terms are involved. In this study, we decided to add the asymptotic stress field up to the third order, because the third order stress vector includes the desired effects such as transverse shear and normal deformations and cross-sectional distortion warping.

3 Numerical Results

The composite beams with closed thin-walled cross-sections are considered as an illustrative example in this paper. The results obtained are compared to

those available in literature to assess the accuracy of the proposed approach. The results obtained correspond to the classical Rankine-Timoshenko theory when considered the shear deformation, while it is comparable to the Vlasov torsion model when considered the warping restrained effect.

3.1 Thin-walled composite box beam

The first example is a cantilevered thin-walled composite beam (Fig. 2) to compare the results with those available in literature. This example is taken from the reference [5], where the material properties and the box beam dimension (height, width and length; 0.53in×0.95in×30in) are described in detail.

Fig. 2. The thin-walled composite box beam dimension and geometry.

In Fig. 3, the bending deflection and bending slope of the beam subjected to the unit tip horizontal shear force. As shown in the figure, the present RTV model outperforms among the theories considered, even it is better than the original asymptotic method in [5].

Fig. 3. The thin-walled composite box beam; a) bending deflection, b) induced deflection; solid line: present, dotted: FAMBA0th, circle: 3D FEM, square: FAMBA2nd, dashed: VABS and others.

3.2 Thin-walled isotropic I-beam

To demonstrate the capability of the present RTV model for torsion problems, the thin-walled isotropic I-beam considered in [7] is taken as the second example (see Fig. 4). A cantilevered thin-walled isotropic subjected to the tip unit torsion is analysed in order to compare the results with the reference.

Fig. 4. Cross-sectional mesh configuration of the thin-walled I-beam.

Fig. 5 shows the first derivative of the torsion angle and the second derivative of the torsion angle along the axial coordinate. The first derivative is closely associated with the torsion, and the second derivative relates to the so-called bi-moment. As shown in Fig. 5(a), it seems that VABS is slightly better than the present approach. However, Fig. 5(b) reveals that such a prediction is inconsistent as compared to what the 3D FEM predicts. One can clearly see that the present approach is able to predict consistently the torsional behavior in terms of the Saint-Venant torsion and bi-moment (or Vlasov torsion).

Fig. 5. The thin-walled isotropic I-beam; a) the first derivative of the torsion angle, b) the second derivative of the torsion angle; solid line: present, dash-dotted: VABS, dotted: 3D FEM.

4 Concluding Remarks

A generalized composite beam theory, which can predict the shear deformation while considering the torsion-restrained effect, is derived systematically via the mixed variational theorem. The independent stress field comes from the asymptotic method, whereas the displacement field is built upon the engineering beam theory. The beam model derived is referred to as the Rankine-Timoshenko-Vlasov (RTV) model in this paper.

The model developed is tested by comparing the results obtained herein with those available in literature. The numerical results obtained clearly demonstrate that the present RTV model outperforms among the results reported in literature including the asymptotic method used to obtain the stress field. Although the results are promising, an intensive parametric study is needed to further assess the accuracy of the RTV model.

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Appendix

The matrices defined in Eq. (1) are given as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & y_2 & y_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & y_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -y_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (A1)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{23} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & ()_{,2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & ()_{,3} \\ 0 & ()_{,3} & ()_{,2} \\ ()_{,3} & 0 & 0 \\ ()_{,2} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{L}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (A2)$$

$$\tilde{\Gamma}_\phi = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & w_1^\phi & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & w_2^\phi & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & w_3^\phi & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (A3)$$

$$\tilde{\Gamma}_{\phi'} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & w_1^\phi \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & w_2^\phi \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & w_3^\phi \end{bmatrix}$$